

Figure 1. The interaction of oseltamivir with Neuraminidase 3CL0.

Figure 2. The interaction of oseltamivir-Phenylalanine.

Interactions

- | | |
|--|---|
| Pi-Cation |
| Pi-Alkyl |
| Carbon Hydrogen Bond | |

Figure 3. The interaction of oseltamivir-Phenylalanine-Hydroxamate

Interactions

	Pi-Cation		
	Alkyl		
	Pi-Alkyl		

Figure 4. Statistical calculations of the dose-response curves of IC50 values for the target oseltamivir carboxamides and their hydroxamate counter parts.

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